

Syntheses of (Z)-7-Tetradecen-1-yl Acetate, (Z)-9-Tetradecen-1-ol and its Acetate from Aleuritic Acid

R. N. MAJEE* and R. RAMANI

Indian Lac Research Institute, Ranchi-834 010

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There had been tremendous interest, during the recent years, in the use of pheromones in insect pest management programme. This is due to concern about environmental pollution and problems of pest resistance to insecticides. Sex pheromones can effectively be used for monitoring the lepidopteran pests and their control through mass trapping, and mate disruption¹. The sex pheromones of a large number of insect species have been analysed, but those of agricultural pests received more attention². (Z)-7-Tetradecen-1-yl acetate, (Z)-9-tetradecen-1-ol and its acetate have been found to occur in the sex pheromones of a few lepidopterous pests^{3,4}. Vig. *et al.*⁵ reported the synthesis of (Z)-7-tetradecen-1-yl acetate (9) from non-2-yn-1-ol. Several synthesis^{6,7} of (Z)-9-tetradecen-1-ol and its acetate have been reported in literature starting from various compounds. Subramanian and Malathi⁸ reported the synthesis of (Z)-9-tetradecen-1-yl acetate (7) from *threo*-aleuritic acid involving a multistep reaction sequence. Aleuritic acid can easily be obtained by alkaline hydrolysis of shellac⁹ which is produced in large quantities in India. A simple synthetic sequence for the compounds 6, 7 and 9 using aleuritic acid as the starting material is reported here.

threo-Aleuritic acid (1) on periodate oxidation¹⁰ yielded 7-hydroxyheptanal (2) and azelaic acid aldehyde (3). It was then converted into its methyl ester (4) using diazomethane. The above ester was subjected to a

stereoselective Wittig olefination with pentyltriphenylphosphonium bromide using NaH in DMSO and THF as co-solvent to give methyl (Z)-9-tetradecenoate (5). Its reduction with LAH/THF gave (Z)-9-tetradecen-1-ol (6)⁴. Treatment of the aforesaid alcohol with acetic anhydride in pyridine yielded (Z)-9-tetradecen-1-yl acetate (7)⁴. 7-Hydroxyheptanal (2) was also subjected as stereoselective Wittig olefination with heptyltriphenylphosphonium bromide using NaH in DMSO and THF as co-solvent to give (Z)-7-tetradecen-1-ol (8). Its treatment with acetic anhydride in pyridine yielded (Z)-7-tetradecen-1-yl acetate (9).

Experimental

B.ps. are uncorrected. Ir and nmr spectra were recorded respectively on a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer and a Perkin-Elmer R-32 instrument (90 MHz) using TMS as an internal standard. The compounds were routinely checked for their purity by tlc.

7-Hydroxyheptanal (2) : A solution of potassium periodate (9.0 g) in 1 N H₂SO₄ (450 ml) at 20° was added rapidly to a stirred solution of *threo*-aleuritic acid (12.0 g) in a methanol-water solution (300 ml; 300 ml at 40°). After 10 min, the mixture was cooled and the solution was extracted immediately with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with brine water and dried (Na₂SO₄). Removal of solvent yielded 7-hydroxyheptanal as liquid (4.74 g) which was purified through a column of neutral alumina by eluting with ether (tlc, single spot) : (Found : C, 64.71; H, 10.72. C₇H₁₄O₂ calcd. for : C, 64.61; H, 10.77%); ν_{\max} 3 250, 1 720 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 2.46 (2H, m, CH₂-CHO), 2.39 (1H, br, CH₂OH, D₂O exchangeable), 3.71 (2H, t, CH₂OH), 9.92 (1H, t, CH₂CHO).

Azelaic acid aldehyde (3) : *threo*-Aleuritic acid (1, 10.0 g) on periodate oxidation following the reported procedure¹⁰ yielded azelaic acid aldehyde (6.25 g) as viscous oil : ν_{\max} 1 725, 1 700 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 1.11–1.81 (10H, m, CH₂COOH), 2.3 (4H, t, CH₂CHO), 9.54 (1H, t, CHO), 9.87 (1H, bs, COOH).

Methyl azelaaldehyde (4) : Compound 3 (5.0 g) was esterified with diazomethane to give 4 (4.6 g) as a liquid, b.p. 90–95°/0.2 mm (lit.¹⁰ 86–92°/0.2 mm); δ (CDCl₃) 1.01–1.89 (10H, m, 5-CH₂), 1.93–2.51 (4H, m, CH₂COOCH₃ and CH₂CHO), 3.61 (3H, s, CO₂CH₃), 8.69 (1H, t, CHO).

Methyl (Z)-9-tetradecenoate (5) : To a stirred solution of NaH (0.4 g, 50% dispersion in oil) in dry DMSO (10

ml), pentyltriphenylphosphonium bromide (3.3 g) in dry DMSO (10 ml) was added for 15 min at 15–20° under N₂ atmosphere. After stirring for 30 min at room temperature, the solution was cooled and methyl azelaldehyde (0.74 g) in dry THF (5 ml) was added dropwise for 1 min at 15°. The mixture was stirred for 10 h at room temperature, then poured into ice-cold water and extracted with ether, washed with water and dried (Na₂SO₄). Removal of solvent gave **5** as a liquid (0.44 g). The product was purified by column chromatography over silica gel : (Found : C, 74.80; H, 11.62. C₁₅H₂₈O₂ calcd. for : C, 75.00; H, 11.66%); ν_{\max} 1 740, 730 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 3.65 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 5.28 (2H, t, CH=CH).

(Z)-9-Tetradecen-1-ol (**6**) : Compound **5** (0.4 g) was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride (0.18 g) in dry tetrahydrofuran (20 ml) at room temperature for 24 h. On usual workup, the alcohol was obtained as a liquid, which was purified by distillation (0.28 g), b.p. 122–126°/0.08 mm (lit.⁷ 120–125°/0.08 mm) (Found : C, 79.69; H, 13.14. C₁₄H₂₈O calcd. for : C, 79.24; H, 13.20%); ν_{\max} 3 205, 2 920, 2 840, 1 435, 1 175, 725 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 0.86 (3H, t, CH₃), 1.26 (16H, br, CH₂), 1.9 (4H, br, CH₂CH=CHCH₂), 3.42 (2H, t, CH₂OH), 5.3 (2H, t, CH=CH).

(Z)-9-Tetradecen-1-yl acetate (**7**) : Acetic anhydride (5.0 ml) was added to a solution **6** (0.2 g) in pyridine (5.0 ml) and stirred for 1 h and kept at room temperature for 24 h. The reaction mixture was then poured into ice-cold water and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed successively with cold dil. HCl, water, aq. NaHCO₃ (5%) and water and dried (Na₂SO₄). Removal of the solvent yielded **7** (0.18 g) as a colourless liquid. The crude product on purification by column chromatography over silica gel using petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°)-ether (80 : 20, v/v) as eluent afforded the product (tlc, single spot) (0.144 g), (Found : C, 75.38; H, 12.00. C₁₆H₃₀O₂ calcd. for : C, 75.59; H, 11.81%); ν_{\max} 2 920, 2 840, 1 725, 1 435, 1 230, 730 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 0.86 (3H, t, CH₃), 1.26 (16H, br, CH₂), 1.9 (4H, br, CH₂CH=CHCH₂), 2.1 (3H, s, -O-CO-CH₃), 4.06 (2H, br, CH₂-OAc), 5.31 (2H, t, CH=CH).

(Z)-7-Tetradecen-1-ol (**8**) : Sodium hydride (0.2 g, 50% dispersion in oil) in dry DMSO (10 ml) was stirred under N₂ atmosphere for 1 h, followed by addition of heptyltriphenylphosphonium bromide (4.1g) in dry DMSO (10 ml) for 15 min at 15–20°. After stirring for 30 min at room temperature, the solution was cooled and then treated dropwise with 7-hydroxyheptanal (**2**; 2.64 g) in dry THF (10 ml). The mixture was stirred for 10 h at room temperature, poured into ice-cold water and extracted with ether, washed with water and dried (Na₂SO₄). Solvent removal gave **8** as liquid residue (1.4 g), which was purified chromatographically over neutral alumina (tlc, single spot) : (Found : C, 79.20; H, 13.13. C₁₄H₂₈O calcd. for : C, 79.24;

H, 13.20%); ν_{\max} 3 425, 2 930, 2 875, 1 040, 730 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 0.91 (3H, t, CH₃), 1.31 (16H, m, saturated CH₂) 2.08 (4H, m, allylic protons), 3.59 (2H, t, CH₂OH), 5.48–5.60 (2H, m, CH=CH).

(Z)-7-Tetradecen-1-yl acetate (**9**) : Compound **8** (0.5 g) was stirred with pyridine (5 ml) and acetic anhydride (5 ml) for 24 h at room temperature. To it little water was added and then extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed successively with cold dil. HCl, water, NaHCO₃ (5%), water and dried (Na₂SO₄). Solvent removal and purification of the crude product over neutral alumina gave **9** (0.34 g) (Found : C, 75.52; H, 11.80. C₁₆H₃₀O₂ calcd. for : C, 75.59; H, 11.81%); ν_{\max} 2 952, 2 880, 1 740, 1 240, 1 035, 730 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 0.94 (3H, t, CH₃), 1.36 (16H, m, saturated CH₂), 2.1 (3H, s, COCH₃), 2.16 (4H, m, allylic methylenes), 3.94 (2H, t, -CH₂-O-CO-), 5.43–5.66 (2H, m, CH=CH).

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